

IMPROVING THE DIDACTIC FUNDAMENTALS OF DESIGNING GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOL LESSONS (ON THE EXAMPLE OF HISTORY)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6554738>

Toshboltayeva Oyshakhon Abdulhamidovna

History teacher at school No. 21 in Namangan district

Annotation: *The article analyzes the importance of designing general secondary education, the essence of the didactic basis, the organization of these areas on the basis of history.*

Keywords: *Secondary education, history, didactic basis, analysis, design.*

Teaching aids, their importance in teaching history, the structure of teaching materials, technical aids. Texts used in the teaching of history in the secondary education system include textbooks, historical documents, works, popular science and art, historical literature, etc. Printed texts are the main source of students' historical knowledge, as well as the source of knowledge of the teacher, the basis of the statement. Naturally, only if the teacher uses these resources correctly and effectively, his statement will meet the requirements of didactics, the high requirements of history education in the secondary education system in general, the teacher's statement will be clear to students, can be meaningful, interesting, ideologically and scientifically convincing, figurative and influential. Working on texts also expands students' knowledge, helps them to better understand the essence of historical facts and events, their laws, forms a scientific worldview, develops historical thinking, they learn to evaluate historical events from a perspective¹.

In the secondary education system, students develop the ability to work independently on a variety of texts and become familiar with the basic methods of historical research. The teacher clarifies and enriches his / her statement based on other texts. Textbooks are an important source for students to study, master and remember history in class and outside of class, to engage in cognitive activities, and to engage in creative research. The text and the questions and assignments in it teach students to master the content of the history course and apply the knowledge in practice. Work on the textbook is different from mastering and memorizing the textbook, analyzing the textbook and finding important signs of historical events, comparing, identifying and summarizing important materials of historical facts and historical facts.

¹ Bepalko V.P. Pedagogy and progressive technologies of training. M., «Pedagogy», 2018.

purposes. Also, when working on the text, master the chronology of ready definitions of historical concepts and independently identify them, follow the development of events and phenomena described in the textbook, learn the traditions of social development based on accurate historical facts and statistics, local, temporal, mastering and defining the laws of cause-and-effect and historical relations, conducting dictionary work with meaningful and descriptive plans, tables and other less complex writing and graphics, the implementation of programmed educational elements on the text tasks are also provided.

When working on historical documents, students need to understand why they are used, when and by whom the documents were created, and what can be learned from them. If there are terms in the documents that are difficult to understand, they are explained on the board, and students write them in a dictionary. Students in grades 5-7 should also be encouraged to work with documents. For example, a 6th grade teacher says, now I'm going to read you an interesting passage from the famous Greek poet Aeschylus's "Persians" about the heroism of the Greeks in the Marathon. There are different ways of working on historical documents².

1. The teacher can analyze the historical document himself.

2. Historical documents can be analyzed by students in the classroom under the direct guidance of the teacher.

3. The teacher can ask students to independently analyze certain documents at home.

4. Divide students into small groups and organize independent work with documents in each group. The teacher reads, analyzes and interprets complex historical documents that are difficult to understand. Students follow the text and listen carefully to the teacher's explanations. In high school, the document is read with commentary. When a teacher asks students questions about a document and raises problems, students' cognitive and thinking activities become more active. In grades VI-VII, the teacher analyzes the document himself, but at the same time teaches students to work with documents. The teacher uses another method of working with documents, which is to analyze the documents with the students. There are easy and difficult places in every text³. Explains complex areas of the text through questions and answers by the teacher or through conversation. Easy places can be assigned to students to read independently. Students will be able to independently read and understand the assignments provided by the teacher if they have been selected

² Mahmudov M. The system of didactic design of educational material. // «Pedagogical skills», 2012, issue 3, pages 3-11.

³ Farberman B.L. Progressivnie pedagogicheskie tekhnologii.-T., 2019

to understand the documents according to their knowledge and skills and have previously practiced working independently on the documents. But even then, the teacher is in charge, and the difficult ones are learned by the teacher, and the easy ones are learned by the students themselves. Economic, legal and other more difficult documents are analyzed under the guidance of a teacher. From 8th grade onwards, some classes are devoted to working on part or all of the lesson paperwork. There is a growing demand for students to work independently in class and at home. Preparation of brief information and abstracts on the basis of historical documents, preparation for storytelling, schematic plan and other graphic work, essay writing, etc. is one of the students' independent creative work on documents. Encourage students to study the documents, which should inspire them. To do this, they need to be reminded that documents are a material monument of a certain period and one of the important sources of new knowledge. When studying a document, it is necessary to explain who created it, when or from what point of view, and the internal and external situation in the country at that time. In the introductory part of the History of the Ancient World, students will gain an understanding of written sources. Later, these concepts will be identified and expanded in the process of studying various written monuments, acquaintance with written monuments in various museums and archives. Thus, historical documents define the teacher's statement, deepen its content, clarify it, make it convincing and emotional, activate students' cognitive activity, thinking, help their knowledge to be thorough and solid, new knowledge acquisition. methods, introduces elementary forms of scientific research.

REFERENCES

1. Bespalko V.P. Pedagogy and progressive technologies of training. M., «Pedagogy», 2018.
2. Bespalko V.P. Pedagogy and progressive technologies of training. M., «Pedagogy», 2019.
3. Mahmudov M. The system of didactic design of educational material. // «Pedagogical skills», 2012, issue 3, pages 3-11.
4. Ochiilov M. New pedagogical technologies. Text of lectures. Karshi, Nasaf, 2018.
5. Farberman B.L. Progressivnie pedagogicheskie tekhnologii.-T., 2019